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Direct Infusion Workflow

Overall study design

Overall study design			
Title of the study	Detection of lipid metabolism after siRNA knockdown of Ppard in primary podocytes		
Document creation date	05/21/2026	Principal investigator	wang haiyan
Institution	nanjing medical university	Corresponding Email	wanghaiyan0124@163.com
Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Untargeted	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Lipid extraction			
Extraction method	1-phase system	pH adjustment	None
1-phase system	Isopropanol	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes

Analytical platform

Analytical platform			
Ionization additives	Ammonium formate, Formic acid	Detector	Mass spectrometer
MS type	QQQ	MS vendor	Waters
Direct type	Syringe	MS Level	MS ¹ , MS ²
Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ¹	Low resolution	Resolution at MS ¹	Unit
Recording mode of raw data at MS ¹	Centroid mode	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	0
Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ²	Low resolution	Resolution at MS ²	Unit
Recording mode of raw data at MS ²	Centroid mode	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No

Quality control

Quality control			
Blanks	Yes	Type of Blanks	Extraction blank
Quality control	Yes	Type of QC sample	Sample pool

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Lipid recovery	No
Dynamic quantification range	Yes	Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes
Precision	Yes	Accuracy	Yes
Guidelines followed	None		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	No	Are metadata available?	Available on request
Raw data upload	Available on request		

Sample Descriptions

siPpard podocyte / Mouse / Cells

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze, Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles, Preservation method
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Instant sample preparation	No
Time to freeze	30	Snap freezing in liquid N2	Yes
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Storage time (month)	0
Freeze-thaw cycles	0	Additives	None

control podocyte / Mouse / Cells

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Provided preanalytical information	Time to separate plasma/serum (min), Time to freeze, Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles, Preservation method
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Instant sample preparation	No
Time to freeze	30	Snap freezing in liquid N2	Yes
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Storage time (month)	0
Freeze-thaw cycles	0	Additives	None
Were samples stored under inert gas?	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Biobank samples	No		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) FA[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	FA	MS Level for identification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ² adduct	[M-H]-
Fragments for identification			

Fragment name

Neutral loss of CO₂

Isotope correction at MS ²	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
MS ² verified by standard	No	Background check at MS ¹	No
Background check at MS ²	No	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A

1) FA[M-H]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹ , MS ²
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Internal lipid standard(s) MS²

Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass
PG(d7)		

Internal lipid standard(s) MS¹

Internal standard	Endogenous subclass
PG(d7)	

Type of quantification	Calibration line	Type of calibration line	Solvent based
Response correction	No	Type I isotope correction	No
Limit of quantification	S/N ratio > 10	Normalization to reference	No
Lipid Quantification Software	None	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Further quantification remarks	None		